

VISIONS OF MEANING FOR IMPACT-ORIENTED INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH IN TIMES OF POLYCRISIS: QUO VADIS?

Workshop Registration Instructions

Prerequisite

In order to participate in the workshop, you must register for the ECIS 2026 conference, as well as the optional workshops. The registration link is: <https://ecis2026.it/registration/>

Participation with Contribution

Simply submit your contribution before the deadline. We will then get in touch to finalize your workshop registration.

Participation without Contribution

To confirm your registration, simply send us an email at either iis-workshop@proton.me or herwix@wiso.uni-koeln.de.

We are looking forward to see you in Milan!